

▼ Smartphone Kimovil Review Vocabulary

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Abstrak: Berikut adalah extended vocabulary dengan menggunakan dataset smartphone review dari website kimovil. Kami memulai pengerjaan dengan membuat vocabulary sendiri. Setelah model telah ditentukan, kami menggantinya dengan vocabulary yang telah umum digunakan. Dalam pengerjaannya, kami mereferensi vocabulary dari schema.org dan juga cookingbigdata.com/linkedata/ccinstances.

▼ Dataset

Dataset ini menunjukkan spesifikasi handphone serta penilaiannya berdasarkan website Kimovil. Dataset ini dapat diakses dari <https://www.kaggle.com/linzy/smartphone-price-compared-by-kimovil-review>

Tabel dataset

```
#load CSV dengan pandas  
#display the table
```

```
from google.colab import files  
uploaded = files.upload()
```

Tidak ada file yang dipilih Upload widget is only available when the cell has been executed in the current browser session. Please rerun this cell to enable.

Saving Smartphone(1it-2it).csv to Smartphone(1it-2it) (1).csv

```
import io, pandas as pd  
data_raw = pd.read_csv(io.BytesIO(uploaded['Smartphone(1jt-2jt).csv']), delimiter=";")  
data_raw
```

	Name	Brand	Price	Processor	RAM	Memory	Screen	Performance	Camera	Connect
0	Alcatel 1S	Alcatel	1.599.000	Mediatek	3	32	4.1	5.7	4.8	
1	Alcatel 1SE	Alcatel	1.599.000	Unisoc	4	64	3.6	5.4	4.9	
2	Zenfone 4 Max	Asus	1.699.000	Snapdragon	3	32	4.1	4.5	3.7	
3	Infinix Hot 10 Play	Infinix	1.259.000	Mediatek	2	32	4.3	5.7	4.6	
4	Nokia C3	Nokia	1.499.000	Unisoc	2	16	3.7	4.3	3.5	
5	Oppo A11	Oppo	1.399.000	Mediatek	2	32	3.9	5.4	4.5	
6	Oppo A15	Oppo	1.799.000	Mediatek	3	32	6.4	5.9	4.7	
7	Oppo A11K	Oppo	1.699.000	Mediatek	2	32	3.9	5.4	4.5	
8	Poco M3	Poco	1.799.000	Snapdragon	4	64	7.0	6.7	6.8	
9	Realme C20	Realme	1.249.000	Mediatek	2	32	5.8	5.8	3.4	
10	Realme C11	Realme	1.429.000	Mediatek	2	32	6.3	5.8	4.4	
11	Realme C21	Realme	1.700.000	Mediatek	3	32	5.1	5.9	4.7	
12	Samsung Galaxy A02s	Samsung	1.999.000	Snapdragon	4	64	3.6	5.4	5.0	
13	Samsung Galaxy A10s	Samsung	1.335.000	Mediatek	2	32	3.6	5.2	4.8	

▼ Vocabulary

Namespace

ex: <https://example.org/>.

rdfs:<http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>.

rdf:<http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>.

xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>.

Kelas smartphone

Properti : produsen, seharga, memilikiRAM, memilikiMemori, memilikiProcessor, url, memilikiReview.

Kelas brand

Properti : namaBrand

Kelas review

Property : screen-review, performance-review, connectivity-review, camera-review, battery-review

```
pip install --no-input jupyter-rdfify
```

```
Collecting jupyter-rdfify
  Downloading jupyter_rdfify-1.0.1-py3-none-any.whl (15 kB)
Collecting PyShEx
  Downloading PyShEx-0.7.20-py3-none-any.whl (51 kB)
```

```
%reload_ext jupyter-rdfify
```

```
DOWNLOADED turtle-0.0.1-py3-none-any.whl (579 kB)
```

```
%%rdf turtle --label Redmi-9A
```

```
#Namespace
```

```
@prefix ex: <https://example.org/>.
@prefix rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>.
@prefix rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>.
@prefix xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>.
```

```
#Class
```

```
ex:smartphone a rdfs:Class.
ex:brand a rdfs:Class.
ex:review a rdfs:Class.
```

```
#Property
```

```
ex:produsen a rdf:property.
ex:produsen rdfs:domain ex:smartphone.
ex:produsen rdfs:range ex:brand.
```

```
ex:namaBrand a rdf:property.
ex:namaBrand rdfs:domain ex:brand.
ex:namaBrand rdfs:range xsd:string.
```

```
ex:seharga a rdf:property.
ex:seharga rdfs:domain ex:smartphone.
ex:seharga rdfs:range xsd:currency.
```

```
ex:memilikiRam a rdf:property.
ex:memilikiRam rdfs:domain ex:smartphone.
ex:memilikiRam rdfs:range ex:gigabyte.
```

```
ex:memilikiMemory a rdf:property.
ex:memilikiMemory rdfs:domain ex:smartphone.
ex:memilikiMemory rdfs:range ex:gigabyte.
```

```
ex:memilikiProcessor a rdf:property.
ex:memilikiProcessor rdfs:domain ex:smartphone.
ex:memilikiProcessor rdfs:range ex:brand.
```

```
ex:url a rdf:property.
ex:url rdfs:domain ex:smartphone.
ex:url rdfs:range xsd:string.
```

```
ex:memilikiReview a rdf:property.
ex:memilikiReview rdfs:domain ex:smartphone.
ex:memilikiReview rdfs:range ex:review.
```

```
ex:screen-review a rdf:property.
ex:screen-review rdfs:domain ex:review.
ex:screen-review rdfs:range xsd:float.
```

ex:performance-review a rdf:property.
ex:performance-review rdfs:domain ex:review.
ex:performance-review rdfs:range xsd:float.

ex:connectivity-review a rdf:property.
ex:connectivity-review rdfs:domain ex:review.
ex:connectivity-review rdfs:range xsd:float.

ex:camera-review a rdf:property.
ex:camera-review rdfs:domain ex:review.
ex:camera-review rdfs:range xsd:float.

ex:battery-review a rdf:property.
ex:battery-review rdfs:domain ex:review.
ex:battery-review rdfs:range xsd:float.

#Instance

ex:xiaomi a ex:brand.
ex:xiaomi ex:namaBrand "Xiaomi"^^xsd:string.
ex:kireview a ex:review.
ex:mediatek a ex:brand.
ex:mediatek ex:namaBrand "Mediatek"^^xsd:string.
ex:redmi9a a ex:smartphone.
ex:redmi9a ex:produsen ex:xiaomi.
ex:redmi9a ex:seharga "1209000"^^xsd:currency.
ex:redmi9a ex:memilikiRam "2"^^ex:gigabyte.
ex:redmi9a ex:memilikiMemory "32"^^ex:gigabyte.
ex:redmi9a ex:memilikiProcessor ex:mediatek.
ex:redmi9a ex:url "<https://www.tokopedia.com/global-teleshop/xiaomi-redmi-9a-smartphone-2-32gb-gray>"
ex:redmi9a ex:memilikiReview ex:kireview.
ex:kireview ex:screen-review "6.5"^^xsd:float.
ex:kireview ex:performance-review "6.3"^^xsd:float.
ex:kireview ex:connectivity-review "7.6"^^xsd:float.
ex:kireview ex:camera-review "6.0"^^xsd:float.
ex:kireview ex:screen-review "8.9"^^xsd:float.

↳ Vocabulary Perpanjangan dari Vocabulary Populer

Namespace

ex: <https://example.org/>.

rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>.

rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>.

xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>.

schema: <http://schema.org/>.

cci: <http://cookingbigdata.com/linkeddata/ccinstances/>.

Kelas Product

Properti : offers, aggregateRating, url, brand

Kelas Brand

Properti : name

Kelas Offer

Properti : price, priceCurrency

Kelas AggregateRating

Properti : ratingValue

Kelas Instance

Properti : hasRAM, hasStorage, hasCPU

Kelas ram

Properti : ram_size

Kelas storage

Properti : storage_size

Kelas cpu :

Properti : cpu_model

```
%%rdf turtle --label Redmi-9A
```

```
#Namespace
```

```
@prefix ex: <https://example.org/>.
```

```
@prefix rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>.
```

```
@prefix rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>.
```

@prefix xsd: <<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>>.
@prefix schema: <<http://schema.org/>>.
@prefix cci: <<http://cookingbigdata.com/linkeddata/ccinstances/>>.

#Class

#Property

#Instance

ex:xiaomi a schema:Brand.

ex:xiaomi schema:name "Xiaomi"^^schema:Text.

ex:redmi9a a schema:Product, cci:Instance.

ex:redmi9a schema:brand ex:xiaomi.

ex:hargaTokopedia a schema:Offer.

ex:redmi9a schema:offers ex:hargaTokopedia.

ex:hargaTokopedia schema:price "1209000"^^schema:Number.

ex:hargaTokopedia schema:priceCurrency "IDR"^^schema:Text.

ex:device_ram a cci:ram.

ex:redmi9a cci:hasRAM ex:device_ram.

ex:device_ram cci:ram_size "2"^^xsd:integer.

ex:device_storage a cci:storage.

ex:redmi9a cci:hasStorage ex:device_storage.

ex:device_storage cci:storage_size "32"^^xsd:integer.

ex:mediatek a cci:cpu.

ex:redmi9a cci:hasCPU ex:mediatek.

ex:mediatek cci:cpu_model "Mediatek"^^xsd:string.

ex:redmi9a schema:url "<https://www.tokopedia.com/global-teleshop/xiaomi-redmi-9a-smartphone-2-32gb-g>

ex:screen_rating a schema:AggregateRating.

ex:redmi9a schema:aggregateRating ex:screen_rating.

ex:screen_rating schema:ratingValue "6.5"^^schema:Number.

ex:performance_rating a schema:AggregateRating.

ex:redmi9a schema:aggregateRating ex:performance_rating.

ex:performance_rating schema:ratingValue "6.3"^^schema:Number.

ex:connectivity_rating a schema:AggregateRating.

ex:redmi9a schema:aggregateRating ex:connectivity_rating.

ex:connectivity_rating schema:ratingValue "7.6"^^schema:Number.

ex:camera_rating a schema:AggregateRating.

ex:redmi9a schema:aggregateRating ex:camera_rating.

ex:camera_rating schema:ratingValue "6.0"^^schema:Number.

ex:battery_rating a schema:AggregateRating.

ex:redmi9a schema:aggregateRating ex:battery_rating.

ex:battery_rating schema:ratingValue "8.9"^^schema:Number.

Daftar Pustaka:

1. Rakhmawati, N. A. (2015). Semantic Web dan Linked Data. Yogyakarta, Indonesia: SiBuku.
2. alamat DOI zenodo python notebook